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Effect of Botulinum Neurotoxin Type A in Induced Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia Male Rats

By
Ghazi Faisal Majid
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A thesis

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Supervised by

**Prof.Dr.
Mustafa Ghazi Alabbassi**

**Assis.Prof.Dr.
Israa Burhan Raof**

2021 A.D.

1443 A.H.

بِسْمِ اللَّهِ الرَّحْمَنِ الرَّحِيمِ

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SUPERVISORY COMMITTEE CERTIFICATE

We certify that the thesis entitled (*Effect of Botulinum Neurotoxin Type A in Induced Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia Male Rats*) was prepared by **Ghazi Faisal Majid** under our supervision at the Department of Pharmacology and Toxicology, College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University as a partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of M.Sc. in Pharmacology and Toxicology.

Signature:

Prof. Dr. Mustafa Ghazi Alabbassi

College of pharmacy

University of Alkafeel

9/2021

Signature:

Assis. Prof. Dr. Israa Burhan Raof

Department of clinical laboratory sciences

College of pharmacy

Mustansiriyah University

13 / 9 / 20 21

In view of the available recommendations, we forward this thesis for debate by examination committee

Signature:

Assis. Prof. Dr. Inam Sameh Arif

Chairman of the Committee of Graduate Studies in the College of Pharmacy/

Mustansiriyah University

/ / 20

EXAMINATION COMMITTEE CERTIFICATE

We, the examination committee, certify that the entitled thesis "Effect of Botulinum Neurotoxin Type A in Induced Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia Male Rats" by Ghazi Faisal Majid has been examined and read through all of its contents and related topics. The committee recommends that the student passed and awarded the degree of M.Sc. in Pharmacology and Toxicology.

Signature:

Prof. Dr. Ghaith Ali Jasim

College of pharmacy

Mustansiriyah University

(Chairman)

Signature:

Prof. Dr. Faris Abdulmawjood Ahmed

College of pharmacy

Uruk University

1 / 20

(Member)

Signature:

Prof. Manal Khalid Abdulridha

College of pharmacy

Mustansyriah University

16 / 19 / 20

(Member)

DEAN CERTIFICATE

This is approved by College of Pharmacy/Mustansiriyah University as a thesis for the degree of Master of Science in Pharmacology and Toxicology.

Signature:

A handwritten signature in green ink, appearing to be 'M. F. Mahdi', written over a horizontal line.

Prof. Dr. Monther Faisal Mahdi

Dean of College of Pharmacy/Mustansiriyah University

/ / 20

DEDICATION

Success is not accident. It is hard work, perseverance, learning, studying, sacrifice
and most of all, love of what you are doing or learning

My family

Whose love and prays

Encourage me to get such success.

Along with all respected

Teachers

They were persistent source of Knowledge

And with my deepest gratitude and sincerest regards,

I dedicate this thesis.

Ghazi Faisal Majid

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Contents	Page No.
Dedication	I
Acknowledgments	II
Table of Contents	III
List of Tables	VII
List of Figures	VIII
List of Abbreviations	XI
Abstract	XV

Chapter One		
1	Introduction	1
1.1	Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia	1
1.2	Rat Prostate Gland Anatomy	2
1.2.1	Macroscopic Anatomy	2
1.2.2	Microscopic Anatomy	3
1.3	Role of Androgen and Androgen Receptor in Prostate Growth	4

1.4	Autonomic Nervous System Control of Rat Prostate Gland	7
1.4.1	Sympathatic system	8
1.4.2	Parasympathetic system	8
1.5	Standard Treatment for Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia	10
1.5.1	α 1 Adrenergic Receptor Antagonists	11
1.5.2	5 α Reductase Inhibitor	12
1.6	Botulinum Neurotoxin Type A	14
1.7	The Current Application of Botulinum Neurotoxin	18
1.8	Nicotine Relation with Prostate Gland Diseases	19
1.9	Prostate Specific Antigen	20
1.10	Inflammation and Tumor Necrosis Factor α Relation to Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia	21
1.11	Apoptosis Relation to Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia	22
1.12	Aim of the Study	23
Chapter Two		
2	Materials and Method	24
2.1	Experimental Design	24
2.2	Expermintal Animal	26
2.3	Materials and Drugs	26
2.4	Dose Calculation and Preparation	27
2.4.1	Dutasteride Dose Calculation and Preparation	27
2.4.2	Alfuzosin Dose Calculation and Preparation	28

2.4.3	Testosterone Propionate Stock Solution Preparation	28
2.4.4	Botulinum Toxin Type A Preparation Intraprostatic Injection Procedure	28
2.4.5	Nicotine Preparation and Administration	29
2.5	Parameter to be Measured	29
2.5.1	Prostate Index	29
2.5.2	Percentage of Prostate Inhibition	30
2.5.3	Calculated Prostate Volume	31
2.5.4	Actual Prostate Volume	31
2.5.5	Ultrasonography for the Ventral Prostate	31
2.5.6	ELISA Test (TNF α , PSA and caspase 3)	32
2.6	Histological Staining Procedure	35
2.7	Statistical analysis	36
Chapter Three		
3	Results	37
3.1	Prostate Index	37
3.2	The Percentage of Prostate Inhibition	39
3.3	Calculated Prostate Volume	40
3.4	Actual Prostate Volume	42
3.5	Ultrasonography of the ventral lobe of the prostate	44
3.6	Serum Level of Tumor Necrosis Factor α	50
3.7	Serum Levels of Prostate Specific Antigen	52

3.8	Serum Caspase 3 Level	55
3.9	Prostate Tissue Homogenate Tumor Necrosis Factor α Concentration	56
3.10	Prostate Tissue Homogenate PSA Concentration	58
3.11	Prostate tissue Caspase 3 Concentration	61
3.12	Histopathological Examination	64
Chapter Four		
4	Discussion	67
5	Conclusion	74
6	Recommendations	75
	References	76

LIST OF TABLES

Table No.	Titles	Page No.
1.1	Comparison between Finasteride, dutasteride and Episteride	14
1.2	The uses of botulinum neurotoxin in the treatment of many diseases	19
2.1	Experimental groups	26
2.2	Drugs and Materials	27
3.1	Prostate index (PI) measured as prostate weight in grams on each 100 grams of rat body weight.	37
3.2	The mean calculated prostate volume in all groups.	40
3.3	Mean actual prostate volume (APV) in ml of each group.	43
3.4	Mean area of the ventral lobe measured by ultrasonography of the prostate gland in all groups.	46
3.5	Mean serum level of TNF α of all groups.	50
3.6	The serum level of prostate specific antigen (PSA) of each rat in all groups with mean serum PSA level of each group.	53
3.7	Mean caspase 3 serum levels of all groups.	55
3.8	Prostates TNF α concentration of all groups.	56
3.9	Prostates PSA concentration of all groups.	59
3.10	Prostate casp3 concentration of all groups.	62

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure No.	Titles	Page No.
1.1	Anatomy of Rat Prostate Gland	2
1.2	Mechanism by which AR receptor activation lead to stimulation of transcription of ARE regulated genes	6
1.3	The postulated mechanism through which botulinum neurotoxin type A cause involution of the prostate gland	7
1.4	The scheme shows that AKT inhibit the apoptosis both premitochondrial before cytochrome release and postmitochondrial through inhibition of caspase 9 activation	10
1.5	The suggested mechanism of action of $\alpha 1$ adrenergic receptor antagonists on the prostate gland.	12
1.6	The physiologic process of neurotransmitter release.	16
1.7	Mechanism of action of botulinum neurotoxin type A and B.	18
1.8	The suggested mechanism of IL1 and TNF α in prostate tissue.	22
2.1	Experiment groups	25
2.2	intraprostatic injection of botulinum neurotoxin type A. Blue arrow represents urinary bladder filled with urine.	29
2.3	Dilution of the standard of the TNF α ELISA kit	33
2.4	The standard dilution steps of PSA ELISA kit	34

2.5	The dilution steps of caspase 3 ELISA kit	35
3.1	The mean Prostate index showed the effect of treatment in group 3 and group4 and increased Prostate index in positive and nicotine group.	39
3.2	The PPI of group3, 4 and 5.	39
3.3	Mean calculated prostate volume (mm ³) on all groups.	42
3.4	Average actual prostate volume on each group.	44
3.5	The mean prostate ventral lobe area using Ultrasonography.	46
3.6	The sonography of the ventral prostate lobules of control group (Group1)	47
3.7	The sonography of the ventral prostate lobules of induction group (Group2)	48
3.8	The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of standard treatment group (Group3)	48
3.9	The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of botulinum group (Group4)	49
3.10	The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of nicotine group (Group5)	49
3.11	Mean serum level of TNF α of each group.	52
3.12	Mean serum PSA level of each group.	54
3.13	Mean serum caspase3 of each group.	56
3.14	The mean concentration of prostate TNF α of each group.	58

3.15	Mean prostate PSA concentration of each group.	61
3.16	Prostate casp3 concentration showed a significant increase in casp3 concentration in the botulinum group.	63
3.17	Hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) stain of rat prostate gland	65

LIST OF ABBRIVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meanings
$\alpha 5nAChR$	$\alpha 5$ nicotinic-acetylcholine receptor
5-AR	5 α reductase
Ach	Acetylcholine
AP-1	Activator protein 1
AR	Androgen receptor
AR-V7	Androgen receptor splice variant 7
ARE	Androgen response element
BPH	Benign prostatic hyperplasia
Casp3	caspase 3
DHT	Dihydrotestosterone

DU145	human prostate cancer cell line
EGF	Epidermal growth factor
ER β	Estrogen receptor β
ERK1/2	Extracellular signal-regulated kinases 1/2
FDA	Food and drug administration
HER2	human epidermal growth factor 2
HSB 40	Heat shock protein 40
HSB 70	Heat shock protein 70
I κ B	Inhibitor of κ B
IGF1	Insulin like growth factor 1
IL1	Interleukin 1
I.P	Intraperitoneal
LUTS	Lower urinary tract symptoms
M3 receptor	Muscarinic receptor 3
MEK4	Mitogen activated protein kinase kinase 4

NF- κ B	Nuclear factor κ B
PC3	human prostate cancer cell line
PI	Prostate index
PI3K	phosphoinositide-3-kinase
PSA	Serum prostate specific antigen
PSG receptor	Polysialognglioside receptor
S.C	Subcutaneous
SNAP 25	Synaptosome-associated protein 25
SV2	Synaptic vesicle protein 2
TNF α	Tumor necrosis factor alpha
TNFR1	Tumor necrosis factor receptor 1
TNFR2	Tumor necrosis factor receptor 2
TGF- β	Transforming growth factor β

VAMP	Vesicle associated membrane protein
VEGF	Vascular endothelial growth factor

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: To explain the mechanism of action and compare the effect of botulinum neurotoxin A with standard treatment (Alfuzosin and dutasteride).

Methodology: Five groups each of them composed of 10 rats. Control group administered normal saline for 42 days. Induction, standard treatment, botulinum and nicotine groups administered testosterone for 14 days. After that, induction group administered normal saline for 28 days. Standard treatment group administered alfuzosin and dutasteride daily for 28 days. Botulinum group administered intraprostatic botulinum neurotoxin A injection. Nicotine group administered intraprostatic botulinum neurotoxin A injection and then administered nicotine for 27 days. Then ultrasonography for ventral prostate is done. After that rats weighed and then sacrificed. Then the prostate gland harvested, weighed, volume measured. ELISA test and histopathological examination carried out.

Results: Botulinum, control and standard treatment groups showed a significant reduction in ventral prostate area when compared with induction and nicotine groups. Botulinum, standard treatment and control groups showed a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) reduction in serum tumor necrosis factor α in comparison with induction and nicotine groups. Botulinum, and control groups showed a significant ($P \leq 0.05$) reduction in serum prostate specific antigen when compared with induction and nicotine groups. Botulinum group express a significant increase of caspase 3 concentrations when compared with control, induction, standard treatment and nicotine groups.

Conclusion: Botulinum neurotoxin A intraprostatic injection reduces hyperplasia may be in part due inhibition of prostate nicotinic receptor activation. Botulinum

neurotoxin A is effective as the standard treatment and have economic advantage of be single injection. Nicotinic receptor may have central role in benign prostatic hyperplasia. The nicotinic receptor may be a new target to develop new drugs to treat benign prostatic hyperplasia. Further studies needed for to compare repetitive doses of Botulinum neurotoxin A with standard treatment.

CHAPTER 1

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia

Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) is a disease that mainly affects elderly male. Half percent of men aged 50 years and 75% of those aged 80 years showed histologic pattern related to BPH, approximately half of BPH patient show significant disease clinically. Lower urinary tract symptom (LUTS) risk increased in BPH. LUTS can be divided into irritation symptom (urination frequency, urgency and pain in urination) and obstructive symptoms (such as incomplete urine emptying) (1).

BPH is characterized by increased both epithelial and stromal cells number in the area of the prostate gland (2).

Although pathophysiology of BPH is not fully understood, it may be caused by androgenic stimulation that lead to prostate gland overgrowth and adrenergic action that lead to contraction of smooth muscle (3). Therefore drugs used for the treatment of BPH are mainly divided into two classes first class is $\alpha 1$ adrenergic antagonist and the second is anti-androgenic drugs such as 5α reductase inhibitor. Rat BPH model can be induced using hormones like testosterone, estrogen and progesterone. This model is typically used to examine drugs that may be having effect to reduce prostate size and BPH disease. There are other rat models such as xenograft models and Genetic engineering techniques (1).

1.2 Rat Prostate Gland Anatomy

1.2.1 Macroscopic Anatomy

Rat prostate gland composed of several lobes. It is composed of four lobes that is the ventral, anterior, dorsal and lateral lobes (4).

Despite that the prostate gland in dogs and human is compact structure that differs from mice and rats which have several lobes, it still useful way to study rat prostate as a model to study human prostate disease. This is because rat prostate controlled by similar mechanisms that control human prostate (4). The anatomy of rat prostate gland showed in figure (1.1).

Figure (1.1): Anatomy of rat prostate gland (5).

1.2.2 Microscopic Anatomy

Rat prostate gland consist of four lobes and each lobe contain pair represent right and lift portion of that lobe. Prostate lobes are covered with a thin capsule. Each lobe composed of acini and ducts that drain to the urethra in independent manner. The acini are isolated by connective tissue containing neurons, nerve ganglia, blood vessels, inflammatory cell, smooth muscle cell and stromal cell. Smooth muscle surround acini and contraction of the smooth muscle release the prostate secretion (4).

The ventral lobe is the largest lobe in rat prostate gland and is located below the urinary bladder. Ventral lobe represents about 50% of the size of the prostate gland. Ventral lobe contain acini of various size covered by columnar epithelium (4).

The dorsal lobe of the prostate gland surrounds the urethra dorsally and located behind the connection between anterior lobe and the seminal vesicle. The acini are small in size and covered by fibromuscular layer that is thin (4).

The lateral lobe of the prostate gland is located just beneath the anterior lobe and seminal vesicle. Anatomic differentiation between dorsal and lateral lobes relatively hard because of similarity in histological features, these lobes are usually considered as one unit, and it is known as the dorsolateral prostate (4).

The anterior lobe of the prostate gland also sometimes called coagulating gland located nearby the seminal vesicle. The acini are firmly packed and covered by fibromuscular capsule (4).

1.3 Role of Androgen and Androgen Receptor in Prostate Growth:

Benign prostatic hyperplasia strictly linked to androgens particularly testosterone and dihydrotestosterone (DHT) (6). Androgens are crucial for differentiation and development of proper structure and function of the prostate gland. Androgen action mediates through binding to androgens receptor (AR), this complex bind to DNA and activates gene transcription. The AR was identified in both epithelial and stromal cell of the rat prostate gland (7).

The AR is a member of the steroid nuclear receptor family. It contains ligand binding domain and DNA binding domain. It is also contain N terminal domain and hinge region. N terminal domain is responsible for the promotion of transcription action of the AR when ligand binding domain available or even when it is not present (8). Hinge region possessed a nuclear localization segment exposed to the ligand binding to AR and it is also permit flexibility between domains. Ligand binding domain had a site to which androgen bind and also contains a site to which coactivator bind and called AF-2 region. DNA binding domain possess domain that bind to androgen response element on DNA causing activation of transcription (9).

When AR is not bound to ligand, AR form a complex in the cytoplasm by binding to the heat shock proteins (HSB40 and HSP70) and co-chaperones (10). This AR complex has conformation that is proper for dihydrotestosterone (DHT) to bind to it. DHT binding to AR induce changes in the conformation of AR complex that lead to dissociation of chaperon from the complex and dimerization of AR receptor. Heat shock protein 27 binding to AR homodimer cause translocation of ligand-receptor from the cytoplasm to the nucleus and its also

facilitate the transcription action of AR. In the nucleus AR recognize androgen response element in DNA leading to transcription of specific genes (9). Researchers discovered that 50% of genes regulated by androgen had a role in the production and modification of the proteins that secreted by prostate tissue (11).

Chronic inflammation that occurs in BPH disease causes infiltration of inflammatory cells that in turn activates nuclear kB (NF-kB). NF-kB cause activation of AR, elevation 5 α reductase 2 and up regulation of androgen receptor splice variant 7 (AR-V7). This leads to increase proliferation of both stromal and epithelial cell (9).

The mechanism by which the activated AR receptor causes stimulation of transcription of androgen response element (ARE) dependent genes showed in figure (1.2).

Figure (1.2): Mechanism by which AR receptor activation lead to stimulation of transcription of androgen response element (ARE) regulated genes (12).

1.4 Autonomic Nervous System Control of Rat Prostate Gland

The postulated mechanism through which autonomic nervous system regulates prostate gland showed in figure (1.3).

Figure (1.3): The postulated mechanism through which botulinum neurotoxin type A cause involution of the prostate gland

Note:[BTXA = botulinum neurotoxin type A, M3R represents muscarinic receptor 3, A1 R = α 1A adrenergic receptors, Ach represents acetylcholine, AR represents androgen receptor, N.E represents norepinephrine and nAChR α 5 denotes nicotinic acetylcholine receptor α 5]. Red arrow represents inhibitory effects. Green arrow refers to stimulatory effect.

1.4.1 Sympathatic System

Rat's prostate innervated by postganglionic fiber that connected from the major pelvic ganglia that innervated by pelvic and hypogastric nerve. Those postganglionic fiber regulate prostate by sympathetic, parasympathetic and peptidergic system (13). The main receptor for sympathetic system in the prostate gland is $\alpha 1A$ receptor (14). The stimulation of $\alpha 1A$ receptor may result in decrease activity of transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β) that in turn lead to decrease level of inhibitor of kappa B α ($I\kappa B\alpha$) that cause activation of NF- κB . This may be result in decrease apoptosis and increased mitosis (15).

1.4.2 Parasympathetic System

The prostate gland is regulated by parasympathetic system through the pelvic nerve that innervate the major pelvic ganglion and the post ganglionic neuron terminate in the prostate gland (16). Cumulative acetylcholine concentration expressed a relaxing effect on the induced prostatic contraction by phenylephrine in isolated prostate tissue from rabbit prostate gland. Studies in rats have found that 5 types of muscarinic receptor available in the rat prostate tissue. Muscarinic 3 receptor subtype have found to cause a contraction in rat prostate tissue (17).

Researches showed that the M3 receptor is up regulated in BPH. Activation of muscarinic receptor results in influx of calcium ion and elevation of calmodulin level. Ca^{+2} /calmodulin signal phosphorylate AKT this lead to proliferation of prostate epithelial cells. It is also cause increase prostate secretion and cause prostate smooth muscle contraction (18).

Nicotinic receptors found in cell membrane of all mammalian cells. These receptors are ionic channels receptor that found in the nervous system and muscle.

Recent researchers found that these receptor also present in other tissue and play a role in many disease such as prostate cancer (19,20).

The $\alpha 5$ Nicotinic acetylcholine receptor ($\alpha 5$ nAChR) found in human prostate gland cell line have a role in growth of prostate gland. The mechanism that lead to activation of growth is that when $\alpha 5$ nAChR is activated that lead to activation of protein kinase B (20). Protein kinase B also known as AKT, the AKT had been shown to increase expression of AR receptor in androgen dependent prostate cancer. AKT showed inhibiting properties against apoptosis by inhibiting the activation of caspase 9. AKT shown to inhibit apoptosis induced by microinjection of cytochrome c in cells overexpressed AKT (21) as showed by figure (1.4).

The activation of $\alpha 5$ nAChR in human PC3 and DU145 cell line also shown to increase Extracellular-signal regulated kinase (ERK)1/2 (20). In mice model the growth of prostate gland inhibited by treatment with PD0325901 an inhibitor of ERK and mTOR inhibitor (22). There are evidence suggest that inhibition of ERK signaling in human prostate cancer cell result in down regulation of prostate cancer (23).

Figure (1.4): The scheme shows AKT cause inhibition of apoptosis (21).

Note: the figure showed that AKT inhibit both premitochondrial before cytochrome release and postmitochondrial through inhibition of caspase 9 activation.

1.5 Standard Treatment for Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia

The European Association of Urology and the American Urological Association recommended two classes of medication. The first group called $\alpha 1$ adrenergic receptor antagonist which composed of four drugs that is doxazosin, alfuzosin, terazosin and tamsulosin. The second group composed of two drugs that are finasteride and dutasteride. Combination therapy of the two classes above result in reduction of progression of BPH significantly when compared with use of one class alone (24).

1.5.1 α 1 Adrenergic Receptor Antagonists

Alfuzosin is the fourth α 1-selective antagonist approved by the FDA for the management of BPH (25). It exerts a selective concentration in the prostate when compared with its level in the blood. Alfuzosin high uroselectivity and its concentration in the urinary tract make alfuzosin have very low adverse effect like vasodilatory effect and little impact in ejaculatory function when compared with other α 1 adrenergic-receptors antagonist (26).

Alfuzosin therapeutic activity is due to its action in the smooth muscle (dynamic component) by antagonizing the action of noradrenaline that released from the nerve ending on the adrenergic receptors (mainly α 1 subtypes) present on the smooth muscle cells of the prostate gland (27).

Some α 1 adrenergic-receptors antagonist like terazosin and doxazosin show the ability to induce apoptosis in the cells of the prostate gland (28). α 1 adrenergic receptor antagonists proposed to inhibit the phosphorylation of phosphoinositide-3-kinase (PI3K) when receptors like epidermal growth factor (EGF), vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) and human epidermal growth factor 2 (HER2) activated. Doxazosin suggested be an inhibitor of topoisomerase 1 and it is also proposed to cause damage the DNA molecule. Quinazolines decrease the inhibitory effect on TGF β that results on increase apoptosis and increase I κ B α . I κ B α increased expression lead to inhibition of NF- κ B (28).

The suggested mechanisms of Quinazolines α 1 adrenergic-receptors antagonist like alfuzosin action in the cells of the prostate gland are expressed below in Figure (1.).

Figure (1.5): The suggested mechanism of action of $\alpha 1$ adrenergic receptor antagonists on the prostate gland (28).

1.5.2 5 α Reductase Inhibitor

Testosterone is the major androgen found in serum and it is mainly produced and secreted by the testes. 5 α reductase is an enzyme responsible for the conversion of testosterone into DHT. DHT have high potency to activate AR more than testosterone. When androgens bind to AR it results in activation of the transcription process of androgen receptor regulated genes. There are three kinds of 5 α reductase isozymes which is 5 α reductase 1(5-AR1), 5 α reductase 2(5-AR2) and 5 α reductase 3 (5-AR3). 5-AR1 is found mainly in the skin and liver but also found in prostate gland in a lower level. 5-AR2 is mainly found in the prostate

gland and other structures that related to the reproductive system. 5-AR3 is found to be highly expressed in prostate cancer and other diseases (6).

Finasteride is an inhibitor of 5-AR2 isozymes where is dutasteride is a dual inhibitor of both 5-AR2 and 5-AR1 (29). Epristeride is a non-competitive inhibitor of 5-AR2 (30).

Table (1.1) showed that the half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of dutasteride is equal to 0.3 ± 0.02 nmol/L for rat 5-AR1 and 0.2 ± 0.04 nmol/L for rats 5-AR2. This mean that dutasteride is more potent than finasteride and episteride in inhibition of both 5-AR1 and 5-AR2 in rats and also humans. The half-life of dutasteride is about 31 hours in rats that is longer than the half-life of finasteride and epristeride which equal to 2 hours and 3 hours respectively. As shown in table (1.1) the chemical structure of finasteride and dutasteride are similar except that in dutasteride the carbomyl group in n17 attached to bis(trifluoromethyl)-phenyl that replace t-butyl moiety of finasteride. This chemical change is responsible for the longer half-life of dutasteride in comparison with finasteride and also responsible for the low IC₅₀ when compared with finasteride or epristeride. These dutasteride features result in it is being a reversible inhibitor of 5-AR1 and irreversible inhibitor dependent in time of 5-AR2 (29).

Despite the fact that 5 α reductase inhibitors considered to be effective in the treatment of BPH but, on the other hand it also has some of adverse effects. It is also require time to reduce symptoms of BPH which make it unsuitable medication to be monotherapy in the treatment of BPH. The most side effects that related to 5 α reductase inhibitors include erectile dysfunction, reduced libido and ejaculation disorders (31).

Table (1.1): Comparison between Finasteride, dutasteride and Epristeride (29).

5 α reductase inhibitor	Model	5AR1 IC50 (nmol/L)	5AR2 IC50 (nmol/L)	Half life in serum
Dutasteride	Humans	6 \pm 1	7 \pm 3	More than 3 days
	Rats	0.3 \pm 0.02	0.2 \pm 0.04	Thirty one hours
Finasteride	Humans	360 \pm 40	69 \pm 1	Six hours
	Rats	5.4 \pm 0.2	0.5 \pm 0.1	Two hours
Epristeride	Humans	350 \pm 50	14.6 \pm 2.4	Twenty seven hours
	Rats	20 \pm 7	11 \pm 1	Three hours

Dutasteride

Finasteride

Note: IC50 represents the half maximal inhibitory concentration (IC50), 5AR= 5 α reductase.

1.6 Botulinum Neurotoxin Type A

Botulinum neurotoxin is derived from type of bacteria called Clostridium botulinum. There are seven subtype of botulinum neurotoxin from A to G. from these seven types only botulinum neurotoxin type A and B used clinically (32).

Pharmacologically active botulinum neurotoxin type A (BTXA) comprising of a light chain (L) and a heavy chain (H) linked by a disulfide bond. Reduction of this disulfide S-S bond releases the light chain which has metalloprotease action. The carboxy-terminal of the C domain of the heavy chain of botulinum neurotoxin type A firstly, binds to polysialoganglioside (PSG) receptors that are existing at a high concentration in the presynaptic membrane. Botulinum neurotoxin type A bind to synaptic vesicle protein 2 (SV2) to enter inside the nerve by a process called endocytosis. After the process of endocytosis, the lumen of the synaptic vesicle showed a neutral pH. Nevertheless, due to the activity of the vesicular ATPase proton pump. This pump physiologically implicated in the buildup of neurotransmitters and protons inside synaptic vesicles. The pH of synaptic

vesicles then is more acidic. This cause change in the conformation of the heavy chain that lead to increase its hydrophobicity forming a channel throw which light chain enter the vesicle. This process is called light chain translocation (33).

Physiologically, neurotransmitters release happens in response to the stimulation of the neurons that result in depolarization of the presynaptic membrane, this stimulation cause the opening of the voltage-dependent Ca^{2+} channels that lead to influx of Ca^{2+} ions into the presynaptic nerve terminal. The raise of Ca^{2+} ions concentration inside the terminals result in binding of Ca^{2+} to Synaptotagmin which stimulates the binding of Synaptotagmin to the SNARE complex figure (1.6) (34). This SNARE complex is composed of vesicle associated-SNAREs (v-SNAREs) which include Vesicle-Associated Membrane Protein (VAMP) and Synaptotagmin and target membrane-SNAREs (t-SNAREs) which include Synaptosome-Associated protein of 25 kDa (SNAP-25) and Syntaxin (35). When the synaptic vesicles reach the plasma membrane of the nerve terminals, SNARE complex formed, in a process that is controlled by complexin , Munc18 and other proteins (34). Membrane fusion lead to transient exposure of the synaptic vesicles to the outside of the nerve ending and neurotransmitter is secreted at the synapase, and the whole process takes just less than milliseconds (36).Neurotransmitters after that can bind to the receptors in |postsynaptic membrane (37). After the neurotransmitters release from the vesicle, vesicles are internalized to the neurons terminals by a process called endocytosis and the recycling (36).

Figure (1.6): The physiologic process of neurotransmitter release (36).

Botulinum neurotoxin type A associate with catalytic activity towards SNAP25 (synaptosomal associated proteins 25) that lead to break of SNAR complex resulting in block of the release of the neurotransmitters from nerve ending (38).

The mechanism that mediate botulinum neurotoxin type A and B action showed in figure (1.7).

Botulinum neurotoxin type A is very powerful toxin which block the neuromascular junction by inhibition of acetylcholine release from nerve ending (39).

The affected neurotransmitters by botulinum neurotoxin type A other than acetylcholine may include norepinephrine and sensory neuropeptide like substance p and ATP. The effect of botulinum neurotoxin type A of the prostate gland related firstly to its effect on growth of prostate gland as its found to result prostate atrophy. Secondly it also decreases contraction of prostate gland smooth muscle and thus effects the dynamic contractions of the prostate gland. injected canine prostate gland with 200 U of botulinum neurotoxin type A found to reduce contractions significantly in prostate gland in response to administration of norepinephrine intravenously (38).

Botulinum neurotoxin effects on the prostate gland not restricted to its action on the neuromascular junction, it may be also associated with its effect on neuro-glandular junction (39).

Intraprostatic injection of botulinum neurotoxin type A can cause involution in the prostate gland without any complication like local inflammation and general systemic adverse effects (39).

Figure (1.7): Mechanism of action of botulinum neurotoxin type A and B (40).

1.7 The Current Application of Botulinum Neurotoxin

Over the past years, botulinum neurotoxin found to have therapeutic effects in many diseases (41).

The uses of botulinum neurotoxin summarized in table (1.2). It found to be effective in the treatment of Strabismus and other eye disorders such as in monocular loss of vision due to secondary strabismus caused by cataract or trauma. It is also have a role in the treatment of movement disorder such as secondary dystonia.

Botulinum neurotoxin used to treat (39–42) Spasticity disorders in many diseases such as multiple sclerosis and traumatic brain injury. It also has become a treatment option for pain such as its use in migraine headache and backache. The role of botulinum neurotoxin in cosmetic is well known (42). Botulinum neurotoxin found to has a role in nose, ear and throat diseases such as its use in pharyngeal and laryngeal disorders. Botulinum neurotoxin also used in other

conditions like hypersecretion of the glands that regulated by parasympathetic system such as increased tearing and hyperhidrosis. The other application of botulinum neurotoxin is in smooth muscle overactivity such as oesophageal disorders (43,44).

Botulinum neurotoxin has a clinical application in diseases that anatomically located near the prostate gland such as anismus, vaginismus, anal fissures and detrusor-sphincter dyssynergia (42).

Table (1.2): The uses of botulinum neurotoxin in the treatment of many diseases (41).

Disease	Approval year for this indication by FDA	Effects
Neurogenic detrusor overactivity	2013	Good efficacy with few side effects
Chronic migraine	2010	Safe and effective but more research needed
Cosmetic use	2012	Very effective and safe in term of long use
Axillary hyperhidrosis	2004	Safe and effective but cause pain at site of injection
Cervical distonya	Many formulation between 2000-2010	Very effective
Strabismus	1989	Very effective
Blepharospasm	1989	Effective
Hemifacial spasm	1989	Effective

1.8 Nicotine Relation with Prostate Gland Diseases

Nicotine is a plant alkaloid (45). It used in the past as an anxiolytic and CNS stimulant (46). It is used clinically as a drug to minimize withdrawal symptom in smoking cessation (47). Nicotine forms up to 1.8% of the dry tobacco weight (48).

Approximately 30% of totally human cancers occur as a result of tobacco and other pollutant. It has been found that tobacco smoking is specifically increase inflammation in prostate carcinoma (49).

The expression of IL8 can be stimulated in the human neutrophil by nicotine. It has been found that IL8 are elevated in tobacco smoker prostate cancer patient. It also found that tobacco smoker prostate cancer patient had increased expression of cytokine. Increased B cell count and activation of NF- κ B in prostate gland (50).

Researchers found that the PSA level increase significantly in BPH patient exposed to tobacco (51).

1.9 Prostate Specific Antigen

Prostate specific antigen (PSA) is a member of kallikrein family and it is produced in epithelial cells of the prostate gland in rats and humans (52,53).

Prostate specific antigen secretion is mainly controlled through androgen receptor signaling pathway in the prostate gland, but PSA level also elevated in androgen independent prostate cancer. It is secreted into the prostate lumen and function to cleave both semenogelin I and semenogelin II in the coagulum of the seminal vesicle. It is used as a biomarker to aid in the diagnosis of the prostate cancer and to monitor treatment response (52).

Inflammation of the prostate glands is a cause other than prostate cancer and hyperplasia that result in elevation of PSA in up to 70% of patient biopsy (54).

Unfortunately, PSA is not a predictive biomarker in early stages of the prostate cancer (52).

Serum PSA cannot be considered as a reliable marker to prostate volume in patient without LUTS because it has a weak relation with prostate volume in those patient (55).

1.10 Inflammation and Tumor Necrosis Factor α Relation to Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia

Tumor necrosis factor α (TNF α) is a cytokine that secreted from many type of immune system cells. TNF α has essential role in the response of the immune system as well as in apoptosis. TNF α and interleukin 1 (IL1) are considered as pro-inflammatory cytokine and express a role in prostate cancer pathogenesis. There are two types of TNF α receptors called TNFR1 that mediate the majority of TNF α effects and TNFR2. Activation of TNFR1 leads to activation of NF- κ B which cause growth and proliferation by expression of anti-apoptotic molecules such as bcl 2 or other growth factor properties. TNFR1 activation also leads to activate MEK 4 (mitogen activated protein kinase kinase 4) which in turn activates JNK (Jun N-terminal kinase) that phosphorylate activator protein 1 (AP-1). AP-1 phosphorylation cause apoptosis through regulation of p38 or cause apoptosis directly (56). The suggested signaling pathway of TNF α and IL1 showed in figure (1.7).

Tumor necrosis factor α antagonists decrease proliferation in epithelial prostate tissue cells and also reduce the expression of NF- κ B. TNF α antagonists also reduce macrophage infiltration. Macrophage releasing TNF α may induce BPH by chronic stimulation of NF- κ B and other inflammatory signaling pathway. Data from mouse models and patient study suggested that necrosis factor alpha antagonism decrease inflammation-mediated hyperplasia in the prostate gland. This support the evidence that TNF α antagonist may be a new treatment for BPH (57).

Figure (1.8): the suggested mechanism of IL1 and TNF α in prostate tissue

1.11 Apoptosis Relation to Benign Prostatic Hyperplasia

The growth of the organ is highly reliant on the balance between proliferation and cell death by apoptosis. Studies indicated that BPH in human is related to increased cell proliferation and abnormal modulation of apoptosis (58).

Disturbance of the molecular mechanisms that control these two processes may be the cause that leads to increased growth of the gland result in the development of BPH. Stimulation of the apoptotic process is controlled by many intracellular factors, such as caspase 3 and Bcl 2. Bcl 2 is a membrane protein in inner mitochondria , the central effect of Bcl 2 increase cell survival by inhibition of apoptosis (59,60).The progress of BPH may be linked with both stromal growth, as a result of active mesenchymal stromal cell proliferation, and the growth of the epithelial cell, caused by decrease glandular apoptosis (58).

1.12 Aim of the Study

To explain the mechanism of action of botulinum neurotoxin A in BPH.
Compare the effect of botulinum neurotoxin A with standard treatment (Alfuzosin and dutasteride).

CHAPTER 2

2 Materials and Method

2.1 Experimental Design

Fifty rats were divided into five groups as shown in figure (2.1) and table (2.1). The first group (group1) is the control group composed of 10 rats administered intraperitoneal injection of 0.5ml of 0.9% normal saline for 43 day.

The second group (group2) composed of 10 rats is the induction group administered testosterone propionate subcutaneous injection 4mg/Kg for 15 day to induce BPH and then administered intraperitoneal injection of 0.5ml/Kg of 0.9% normal saline for 28 day.

The third group (group3) of 10 rats is the standard treatment group administered subcutaneous injection of testosterone propionate 4mg/Kg daily for 15 day to induce BPH. Then rats on this group administered combination therapy of alfuzosin hydrochloride 0.88mg/Kg and dutasteride 0.44mg/Kg. This combination administered by oral gavage daily for 28 day.

The fourth group (group4) which is the botulinum group composed of 10 rats administered subcutaneous injection of testosterone propionate 4mg/Kg daily for 15 day to induce BPH. Then rats of this group were administered intraprostatic injection of 5 units into the ventral lobe of the prostate. Then rats in this group were monitored for any behavior or other abnormality for 27 days.

The fifth group (group5) is nicotine group composed of 10 rats, BPH induced by subcutaneous injection of testosterone propionate 4mg/Kg daily for 15 day. Then rats administered intraprostatic botulinum toxin 5 units into the ventral lobe of the prostate at day 15. Rats in this group then administered 0.1mg/Kg nicotine

orally every day for 27 days and monitored for any behavior or other abnormality for during the experiment. Rats prepared and ultrasonography is done for ventral lobe of the prostate gland.

Figure (2.1): Experiment groups

Rats of all groups were weighed and then sacrificed by intraperitoneal injection of 200mg/Kg phenobarbital (61). Then the prostate gland were harvested, weighed and cut into two parts one fixed by formaldehyde 10% for histopathological examination and the other part were homogenized to detect tissue biomarker by ELISA.

Table (2.1): Experimental groups

Group name	Rats number	Treatment type and duration
Control group	Ten	Normal saline I.P for 43 days
Induction group	Ten	BPH induction 15 days + normal saline 28 days
Standard treatment group	Ten	BPH induction 15 days + combination 28 days
Botulinum group	Ten	BPH induction 15 days + BTXA + 27 days free
Nicotine group	Ten	BPH induction 15 days + BTXA + nicotine for 27 days

Note: Where I.P = intraperitoneal, BPH = benign prostatic hyperplasia, BTXA = botulinum neurotoxin type A.

2.2 Experimental Animal

Fifty Adult male Wister rats 250-350 gram purchased from the Iraqi centre for genetics and cancer research.

Animals is kept in normal room temperature approximately 21°C and sustained at 12 dark/light cycle with maintenance of free food and water access.

2.3 Materials and Drugs

The drugs and materials used in the experiment showed in table (2-2).

Table (2-2): Drugs and materials

Drugs or materials	Company	Country
Testosterone propionate	MH pharma.Co.LTD	Pakistan
Pure olive oil	Naturel	Spain
Alfuzosin (Xatral)	Sanofi	France
Dutasteride (Avodart)	GSK	UK
Botulinum neurotoxin A (Hutox)	Huons-Global Co.Ltd	South korea
Nicotine lozenges	Johnson & Johnson	USA
Xylazine	Kepto	Holland
Ketamine	Bremer Pharma GmbH	Germany
TNF α ELISA kit	Sunlong Biotech Co LTD	China
PSA ELISA kit	Sunlong Biotech Co LTD	China
Caspase 3 ELISA kit	Sunlong Biotech Co LTD	China

2.4 Dose Calculation and Preparation

2.4.1 Dutasteride Dose Calculation and Preparation

The dose of dutasteride used 0.044mg/Kg/day. Rat dose of dutasteride was calculated by multiply human dose with 6.2 (conversion factor according to FDA). For 70Kg human aminister 0.5 mg/day, so the dose will be 0.00714mg/Kg/day. Multiplying the dose by conversion factor between rats and human will give us the dose for rats: $0.00714\text{mg/Kg/day} * 6.2 = 0.044\text{ mg/Kg/day}$. (Avodart capsules diluted with olive oil to prepare 0.11mg/ml) (62).

2.4.2 Alfuzosin Dose Calculation and Preparation

The human dose of alfuzosin for treatment of BPH is 2.5-10 mg per day. For conversion of the human dose to rat dose by multiply human dose with 6.2 (conversion factor according to FDA). For 70Kg human who take 10 mg per day the dose will be 0.142mg/Kg/day (63). The alfuzosin doses of rat obtained by multiplying the human dose by the conversion factor.

Rat dose = $0.142\text{mg/kg/day} * 6.2 = 0.88 \text{ mg/kg/day}$. Alfuzosin diluted with distilled water to prepare stock solution of 2.2mg/ml.

2.4.3 Testosterone Propionate Stock Solution Preparation

Testosterone propionate was added to olive oil to prepare stock solution of 20mg/ml. The dose for BPH induction was 4mg/kg/day for 14 days (64).

2.4.4 Botulinum Toxin Type A Preparation and Intraprostatic Injection Procedure

Botulinum neurotoxin vial contain 100 unit of the toxin. The vial was dissolved with 4ml of 0.9% normal saline to prepare stock solution of 25 unit/ml (65). Rats were anesthetized with 50mg/Kg ketamine injected intraperitoneally plus intraperitoneal injection of 12mg/Kg xylazine. The lower abdominal hair was removed by shaver and the incision area dis-infected with povidone iodine 10% and 70% ethyl alcohol. A lower abdominal small incision about 2 cm was made at the midline and the prostate gland together exposed for injection syringe by remove of the surrounding tissue carefully (61). Botulinum toxin intraprostatic injection showed in figure (2.1).

Figure (2.2): intraprostatic injection of botulinum neurotoxin type A. Blue arrow represents urinary bladder filled with urine. Red arrow represents the ventral lobe of the prostate gland.

The injection process run out by 1ml syringe of 27 gage. Ventral lobe of the prostate gland was injected with 0.2 ml of botulinum toxin stock solution. Care was taken to inject 0.1ml on each lobule of the ventral lobe of the prostate. The injected area then cleaned. After that the wound of the skin and wall of the abdomen closed using 0/4 PGA suturing and disinfected with povidone iodine 10% (61).

2.4.5 Nicotine Preparation and Administration

Nicotine solution was prepared by dissolving one lozenge containing 2mg of nicotine in 8ml normal saline to prepare stock solution of 0.25mg/ml. Rats were administered 0.1 mg/Kg orally (66).

2.5 Parameter to be Measured

2.5.1 Prostate Index

Prostate index (PI) calculated from the formula:

$PI = (\text{Prostate weight} * 100) / \text{Rat body weight}.$

Unit of PI=gram/100gram (62).

2.5.2 Percentage of Prostate Inhibition

Percentage of prostate inhibition (PPI) of Group3 (PPI3) = $\{100 - [(API.C - API.N) / (API.I - API.N)]\} * 100\%$.

Where is:

API.C = Average prostate index of standard treatment group.

API.N = Average prostate index of control group.

API.I = Average prostate index of induction group.

Percentage of prostate inhibition of Group4 (PPI4) = $\{100 - [(API.B - API.N) / (API.I - API.N)]\} * 100\%$

Where is:

API.B = Average prostate index of botulinum group.

API.N = Average prostate index of control group.

API.I = Average prostate index of induction group.

Percentage of prostate inhibition of Group5 (PPI5) = $\{100 - [(API.NIC - API.N) / (API.I - API.N)]\} * 100\%$

Where is:

API.NIC = Average prostate index of nicotine group.

API.N = Average prostate index of control group.

API.I = Average prostate index of induction group (67).

2.5.3 Calculated Prostate Volume

After the prostate dissected a vernier caliper used to detect the length, width and height of the prostate gland and the calculated prostate volume (CPV) obtained by the formula below (63):

$$\text{CPV} = (\text{Length} * \text{width} * \text{height})/2$$

2.5.4 Actual prostate volume

The actual prostate volume (APV) is measured by fluid displacement according to Archimedes principle. APV calculated through the use of 5 ml graduated cylinder filled with 200 ml phosphate buffer saline (PH=7.4) and called the initial volume. The whole prostate gland immersed in the graduated cylinder and the entire volume is written and called the final volume (68). The Actual prostate volume is calculated from the formula:

$$\text{Actual prostate volume (APV)} = \text{Final volume} - \text{Initial volume.}$$

2.5.5 Ultrasonography for the Ventral Prostate

Two dimension sonography done by HONDA ELECTROSONICS HS—2000 VET using linear probe with 10MHz frequency.

Rats were firstly had been anesthetized with ketamine 50 mg/kg and xylazine 12mg/kg combination then rats abdomen shaved using electrical shaver. Secondly

ultrasound gel water soluble (ECO super gel) applied to rat's abdomen after rats had been placed in supine position. Lastly ultrasonography were made by applying 10 MHz linear probe over the prostate location in rat abdomen after that the sonography had been made using by HONDA ELECTROSONICS HS—2000 VET sonographer. The area of the ventral prostate (VPA) calculated using the formula:

$VPA = \pi * r1 * r2$. Where is $r1 =$ radius one and $r2 =$ radius 2. (ellipsoid formula). The area calculated for right ventral prostate and left ventral prostate and the summation represented the VPA (69).

2.5.6 ELISA Test

2.5.6.1 ELISA Test for Biomarkers in Serum

ELISA kit purchased from Sunlong Biotech Co LTD. According to the instruction of Sunlong Biotech Co LTD provided with the kit. Blood samples collected from heart puncture by 5 cc syringe. Blood allowed for clotting by leaving it undisturbed at 25°C for 20 minutes. The clot removed by centrifuging at 3,000 rpm for 20 minutes.

ELISA test is done for determination of serum level of tumor necrosis factor α (TNF α) (70), prostate specific antigen (PSA) (71) and caspase 3 (casp3) (72).

2.5.6.2 ELISA Test for Biomarkers in Prostate Tissue Homogenate

ELISA kit for tissue purchased from Sunlong Biotech Co LTD. According to the instruction of Sunlong Biotech Co LTD provided with the kit. Prostate tissue were cut and homogenised after adding phosphor buffer saline 9 times the prostate tissue weight. The supernatant collected after centrifuging at 3,000 rpm for 20 minutes. ELISA test is done for serum concentration of the following biomarker:

ELISA test is done for determination of serum level of tumor necrosis factor α (TNF α) (70), prostate specific antigen (PSA) (71) and caspase 3 (casp3) (72).

2.5.6.3 Procedure of ELISA Test for Plasma and prostate tissue homogenate

a) Tumor necrosis factor α : The standard diluted by small tubes firstly, then volume of 50 μ l from each tube was added to microplate well. The dilution steps showed in figure (2.3).

Figure (2.3): Dilution of the standard of the TNF α ELISA kit

In the Microelisa stripplate, well left empty as blank control. In sample wells, 40 μ l Sample dilution buffer and 10 μ l sample are added. Then samples loaded onto the bottom without touching the well wall. Mix well with gentle shaking. Then the stripplate incubated half hour at 37°C. Washing buffer diluted with distilled water. Washing of the microelisa stripplate after that repeated 5 times. Fifty μ l HRP-Conjugate reagent was added to each well except the blank control well. Then incubation and washing process repeated. Fifty μ l Chromogen Solution A and 50 μ l Chromogen Solution B was added to each well. Then incubation for 15 minute at 37 °C. Fifty μ l stop solution was added to each well to terminate the reaction. Absorbance O.D. was read at 450nm using a Microtiter Plate Reader (70, 73).

- b) Prostate specific antigen: Dilution of Standards described in figure (2.4). Ten wells are set for standards in a Microelisa stripplate.

Figure (2.4): The standard dilution steps of PSA ELISA kit

In the Microelisa stripplate, well left empty as blank control. In sample wells, 40 μ l Sample dilution buffer and 10 μ l sample are added. Then samples loaded onto the bottom without touching the well wall. Mix well with gentle shaking. Then the stripplate incubated 30 min at 37°C after sealed with Closure plate membrane. washing buffer diluted with distilled water. Washing after that repeated 5 times. Fifty μ l HRP-Conjugate reagent added to each well except the blank control well. Then incubation and washing process repeated. Fifty μ l Chromogen Solution A and 50 μ l Chromogen Solution B was added to each well. Then, incubation process was done for 15 minute at 37 °C. Fifty μ l stop solution was added to each well to terminate the reaction. Absorbance O.D. was read at 450nm using a Microtiter Plate Reader (71, 73).

- c) Caspase 3: The dilution steps showed in the figure (11). Ten wells are set for standards in a Microelisa stripplate. In the Microelisa stripplate, well left as blank control. In sample wells, 40 μ l Sample dilution buffer and 10 μ l sample are added. Then samples loaded onto the bottom without touching the well wall.

Mix well with gentle shaking. Then the stripplate incubated 30 min at 37°C after sealed with Closure plate membrane. Washing buffer diluted with distilled water. Washing after that repeated 5 times. Fifty µl HRP-Conjugate reagent added to each well except the blank control well. Then incubation and washing process repeated. Fifty µl Chromogen Solution A and 50 µl Chromogen Solution B was added to each well. Then, incubation process was done for 15 minute at 37 °C. Fifty µl stop solution was added to each well to terminate the reaction. Absorbance O.D. was read at 450nm using a Microtiter Plate Reader (72, 73).

Figure (2.5): The dilution steps of caspase 3 ELISA kit

2.6 Histological Staining Procedure

The prostate tissue cut and fixed in 10% formaldehyde. Prostate tissue then treated with alcohol 70%, 80 %, 90 % and absolute concentration of alcohol. The slide immersed in paraffin. Paraffin cleared using xylene. The slide cut at 4 micrometre using microtome. The slide then immersed in absolute, 90%, 80 and 70% alcohol in that order. The slide washed in water for 1 minute, stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The slide after that washed with water. The slide treated with 70%, 80%, 90% and absolute concentration of alcohol. Lastly, the slide cleared using xylene. The slide read using microscope (74).

2.7 Statistical Analysis

The results analysis by using SPSS and value of each result expressed as a mean \pm S.D (standard deviation). The post hoc test was used, and p value ≤ 0.05 was considered significant. P value > 0.05 was considered as no significant difference.

CHAPTER 3

3 RESULTS

3.1 Prostate Index

There were a significant reduction in prostate index (PI) on the botulinum group in comparing with the induction group (p value ≤ 0.05). On the other hand there were no significant increase in PI between the botulinum group and the control group (p value = 0.233). The results of the PI in all groups are shown in table (3.1).

Table (3.1): Prostate index (PI) measured as prostate weight in grams on each 100 grams of rat body weight

Rat group	Mean g/100g \pm S.D
Control group	0.208 \pm 0.045
Induction group	0.317 \pm 0.053
Standard treatment group	0.244 \pm 0.025 * #
Botulinum group	0.239 \pm 0.056 * #
Nicotine group	0.338 \pm 0.088 ** ##

Prostate index in g/100g expressed as mean \pm S.D. S.D represents the standard deviation. Where is * represent there is a significant decrease in PI in comparison with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05), # represent a no significant increase in PI in comparison with control (P value > 0.05), ** significant increase in PI in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05) and ## no significant decrease in PI in comparison with induction group (P value > 0.05).

Control group (Group1) had a mean prostate index equal to 0.208 ± 0.045 g/100g. Control group had no significant decrease in PI when compared with standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value = 0.165 and 0.233 respectively). Control group had a significant decrease in PI when compared with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05).

Induction group (Group2) had a mean prostate index equal to 0.317 ± 0.053 g/100g. Induction group showed significant increase in PI with control group, standard treatment group and botulinum group (P value ≤ 0.05). Induction group had no significant decrease in PI in comparison with nicotine group (P value = 0.412).

Standard treatment group showed a mean prostate index equal to 0.244 ± 0.025 g/100g. Standard treatment group had significant decrease in PI in comparison with Induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). Standard treatment group showed no significant increase in PI when compared with control group and botulinum group (p value = 0.165 and 0.839 respectively).

Botulinum group (Group4) showed a mean PI equal to 0.239 ± 0.056 g/100g. Botulinum group showed a significant decrease in PI with Induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). It is also showed no significant increase in PI when compared with control and standard treatment groups (p value = 0,233 and 0.839 respectively).

Nicotine group (group5) possessed a PI mean equal to 0.338 ± 0.088 g/100g. Nicotine group owned a significant increase in PI in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

The average PI represented in the figure (3.1) show that treatment group3 and group4 are closed to the average PI of control group. It is also show that nicotine group average PI is larger than that of the induction group.

Figure (3.1): The mean Prostate index of group 3, 4 and increased Prostate index in positive and nicotine group

Control, standard treatment and nicotine groups showed significant decrease in PI in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

3.2 The Percentage of Prostate Inhibition

The percentage of prostate inhibition (PPI) of the standard treatment, botulinum and nicotine groups equal to 66.7%, 71.5% and -19.5% respectively. The PPI of standard treatment, botulinum and nicotine group showed in figure (3.2).

Figure (3.2): The PPI of Group3, 4 and 5. Group3 and 4 inhibit prostate by 66.7% and 71.5% respectively. Group5 increase prostate growth by 19.5%

3.3 Calculated Prostate Volume

Standard treatment group and botulinum group had a significant reduction in the calculated prostate volume (CPV) when compared with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05). On the other side botulinum group showed no significant increase in CPV in comparison with control group (p value equal to 0.081). The mean calculated prostate volume of all groups presented in the table (3.2).

Table (3.2): The mean calculated prostate volume in all groups

Rats group	Mean mm ³ \pm S.D
Control group	370.1 \pm 100.3
Induction group	997.9 \pm 148.6
Standard treatment group	468 \pm 123.4 *
Botulinum group	472.6 \pm 62 * #
Nicotine group	845 \pm 177 **

The calculated prostate volume in mm³ expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. Where is * represent there is a significant decrease in CPV in comparison with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05), # represent a no significant increase in CPV in comparison with control and standard treatment groups (P value > 0.05), ** significant increase in CPV in comparison with control, standard treatment, botulinum groups and induction groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

Control group (Group1) possessed mean calculated prostate volume equal to 370.1 \pm 100.3 mm³. Control group expressed a significant decrease in CPV in paralleling with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). Control group had no significant decrease in CPV in comparison with standard treatment and botulinum group (p value = 0.095 and 0.081 in that order).

Induction group had a mean calculated prostate volume equal to 997.9 \pm 148.6 mm³. Induction group showed a significant increase in calculated prostate volume when matched against the control group, standard treatment group, botulinum group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05).

Standard treatment group had a mean calculated prostate volume equal to $468 \pm 123.4 \text{ mm}^3$. Standard treatment group express a significant decrease in CPV as compared with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). Standard treatment group showed no significant increase in CPV in comparison with control group and botulinum group (p value 0.095 and 0.937 in that order).

Botulinum group possessed a mean calculated prostate volume of $472.6 \pm 62 \text{ mm}^3$. Botulinum group express no significant increase in CPV when compared with control and standard treatment groups (p value = 0.081 and 0.937 respectively). Botulinum group showed significant decrease in CPV with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05).

Nicotine group had a mean calculated prostate volume equal to $845 \pm 177 \text{ mm}^3$. Nicotine group express significant increase in CPV when compared with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group expressed significant decrease in CPV when compared with induction group. The average calculated prostate volume represented in figure (3.3).

Figure (3.3): Mean calculated prostate volume (mm^3) on all groups. Control, standard treatment and botulinum groups showed significant decrease in CPV in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05)

3.4 Actual Prostate Volume

Botulinum group expressed a significant reduction in actual prostate volume (APV) as compared with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05). The mean actual prostate volume of all groups represented in the table (3.3).

Control group showed mean actual prostate volume equal to 330 ± 67.4 ml. Control group expressed no significant decrease in APV when compared with standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value = 0.338 and 0.383 respectively). Control group possessed a significant decrease in APV when compared with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

Induction group had a mean actual prostate volume equal to 825 ± 139.9 ml. Induction group showed a significant increase in APV with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Induction group possessed a no significant decrease in APV when compared with nicotine group (P value = 0.726).

Table (3.3): Mean actual prostate volume (APV) in ml of each group

Rats group	Mean ml \pm S.D
Control group	330 \pm 67.4
Induction group	825 \pm 139.9
Standard treatment group	385 \pm 127 * #
Botulinum group	380 \pm 94.8 * #
Nicotine group	845 \pm 177 ** ##

The actual prostate volume in ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. Where is * represent there is a significant decrease in APV in comparison with induction group (P value \leq 0.05), # represent a no significant increase in APV in comparison with control (P value $>$ 0.05), ** significant increase in APV in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value \leq 0.05) and ## no significant increase in APV in comparison with induction group (P value $>$ 0.05).

Standard treatment group showed a mean actual prostate volume equal to 385 \pm 127 ml. Standard treatment group had a significant decrease in APV in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (P value \leq 0.05). Standard treatment group showed a no significant increase in APV in comparison with control group and botulinum group (P value = 0.338 and 0.930 respectively).

Botulinum group had a mean actual prostate volume equal to 380 \pm 94.8 ml. Botulinum group possessed a significant decrease in APV in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (P value \leq 0.05). Botulinum group had a no significant increase in APV in comparison with control group and standard treatment group (P value = 0.383 and 0.930 respectively).

Nicotine group had a mean actual prostate volume equal to 845 \pm 177 ml. Nicotine group showed a significant increase in APV when compared with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value \leq 0.05). Nicotine group showed

no significant increase in actual prostate volume with induction group (P value = 0.726). The mean actual prostate volume (APV) represented in figure (3.4).

Figure (3.4): Average actual prostate volume on each group.

Control, standard treatment and botulinum groups showed a significant decrease in APV in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

3.5 Ultrasonography of the Ventral Lobe of the Prostate

Botulinum group had a significant reduction in the area of the ventral lobe (VPA) of the prostate in relation with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05).

The area of the two lobule of the ventral lobe of the prostate gland on each group was represented in table (3.4). Control group showed a mean VPA equal to $328.2 \pm 76 \text{mm}^2$. Control group expressed no significant decrease in VPA in comparison with standard treatment and botulinum groups (p value = 0.284 and 0.163 respectively). Control group possessed a significant decrease in VPA in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

Induction group had a mean VPA equal to $700.6 \pm 77 \text{ mm}^2$. Induction group showed a significant increase in VPA in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups in VPA (P value ≤ 0.05). Induction group possessed a no significant decrease in VPA when compared with nicotine group (P value = 0.4).

Standard treatment group possessed a mean VPA equal to $405.7 \pm 148 \text{ mm}^2$. Standard treatment group had a significant decrease in VPA in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). Standard treatment group expressed no significant increase in VPA in comparison with control and botulinum groups (P value = 0.2 and 0.7 respectively).

Botulinum group had a mean VPA equal to $429.7 \pm 173 \text{ mm}^2$. Botulinum group possessed a significant decrease in VPA in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Botulinum group had a no significant difference in comparison with control and standard treatment groups (P value = 0.1 and 0.7 respectively).

Nicotine group had a mean VPA equal to $758.7 \pm 252 \text{ mm}^2$. Nicotine group showed a significant increase in VPA when compared with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group showed no significant increase in actual prostate volume with induction group (P value = 0.4).

Table (3.4): Mean area of the ventral lobe measured by ultrasonography of the prostate gland in all groups.

Rats group	Mean mm ² ± S.D
Control group	328.2 mm ² ± 76
Induction group	700.6 mm ² ± 77
Standard treatment group	405.7 mm ² ± 148 * #
Botulinum group	429.7 mm ² ± 173 * #
Nicotine group	758.7 mm ² ± 252 ** ##

Mean area of the ventral lobe of the prostate gland mm² expressed in mean ± S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. Where is * represent there is a significant decrease in VPA in comparison with induction group (P value ≤ 0.05), # represent a no significant increase in VPA in comparison with control (P value > 0.05), ** significant increase in VPA in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05) and ## no significant increase in VPA in comparison with induction group (P value > 0.05).

The average VPA of each group represented in the figure (3.5).

Figure (3.5): The mean prostate ventral lobe area using Ultrasonography. Control, standard treatment and botulinum groups showed a significant decrease in APV in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05).

The sonography of rats number 1 and 6 on the control group shown in figure (3.6).

Figure (3.6): The sonography of the ventral prostate lobules of control group (Group1).

Note: (A) sonography of rat number one which had a ventral prostate area equal to 466mm^2 and (B) sonography of rat number six which had a ventral prostate area equal to 368.88mm^2 . [Note: The symbols (+) radius1 and (x) radius2].

The sonography of rat number 3 and 7 on the induction group (Group2) shown in figure (3.7).

Figure (3.7): The sonography of the ventral prostate lobules of induction group.

Note:(A) sonography of rat number three which had a ventral prostate area equal to 709.32 mm^2 (B) sonography of rat number seven which had a ventral prostate area equal to 802.67 mm^2 . [Note: The symbols (+) radius1 and (x) radius2].

The sonography of rats number 3 and 5 on the standard treatment group shown in figure (3.8).

Figure (3.8): The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of standard treatment group (Group3).

Note:(A) represent the sonography of rat number three which had a ventral prostate area equal to 280.27 mm^2 and (B) represent the sonography of rat number 5 which had a ventral prostate area equal to 241.9 mm^2 . [Note: The symbols (+) radius1 and (x) radius2].

The sonography of rat number 4 and 5 on the botulinum group (Group4) shown in figure (3.9).

Figure (3.9): The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of botulinum group (Group4).

Note:(A) represent the sonography of rat number four which had a ventral prostate area equal to 437.84mm² and (B) represent the sonography of rat number five which had a ventral prostate area equal to 354.22mm². [Note: The symbols (+) radius1 and (x) radius2].

The sonography of rat number 6 and 7 on the nicotine group (Group5) shown in figure (3.10).

Figure (3.10): The sonography of ventral prostate lobule of nicotine group (Group5)

Note:(A) represent the sonography of rat number six which had a ventral prostate area equal to 346.97mm² and (B) represent the sonography of rat number seven

which had a ventral prostate area equal to 605.01mm^2 . [Note: The symbols (+) radius1 and (x) radius2].

3.6 Serum Level of Tumor Necrosis Factor α

There were a significant reduction in serum TNF α level on the botulinum group in comparing with the induction group (p value = 1.83×10^{-4}). On the other hand there were no significant increase in TNF α between the botulinum group and the control group (p value = 0.651). The level of serum TNF α of each rat on each group and the average of TNF α of each group represented in table (3.5).

Table (3.5): Mean serum level of TNF α of all groups

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	78.2 \pm 34.195
Induction group	139.23 \pm 34.69
Standard treatment group	99.545 \pm 27.78 * #
Botulinum group	84.327 \pm 28.06 * #
Nicotine group	157.836 \pm 24.517 ** ##

The serum level of TNF α ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. the S.D represents the standard deviation. Where is * represent there is a significant decrease in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with induction group (P value \leq 0.05), # represent a no significant increase in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with control group (P value $>$ 0.05), ** significant increase in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value \leq 0.05) and ## no significant increase in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with induction group (P value $>$ 0.05).

Control group showed a mean serum TNF α level equal to 78.2 ng/ml. Control group expressed no significant decrease in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with standard treatment and botulinum groups (p value = 0.120 and 0.651 respectively). Control group possessed a significant decrease in the serum level of TNF α in comparison with induction with and nicotine group (P value \leq 0.05).

Induction group had a mean serum TNF α level equal to 139.23 ng/ml. Induction group showed a significant increase in serum TNF α level when

compared with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Induction group possessed a no significant decrease in serum TNF α level when compared with nicotine group (P value = 0.174).

Standard treatment group possessed a mean serum TNF α level equal to 99.54 ng/ml. Standard treatment group showed a significant decrease in the serum TNF α level in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (P value ≤ 0.05). Standard treatment group expressed no significant increase in serum TNF α level when compared with control group and botulinum group (P value = 0.12 and 0.264 respectively).

Botulinum group had a mean serum TNF α level equal to 84.32 ng/ml. Botulinum group possessed a significant decrease in Serum TNF α level in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Botulinum group had a no significant increase in the level of serum TNF α in comparison with control and standard treatment groups (P value = 0.651 and 0.264 respectively).

Nicotine group had a mean serum level of TNF α equal to 157.83 ng/ml . Nicotine group showed a significant increase in the level of serum TNF α when compared with control, standard treatment and botulinum groups (P value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group showed no significant increase in serum level of TNF α with induction group (P value = 0.174). The mean serum TNF α level of each group represented in figure (3.11).

Figure (3.11): Mean serum level of TNF α of each group.

Control, standard treatment and botulinum groups showed a significant difference in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (p value ≤ 0.05).

3.7 Serum Levels of Prostate Specific Antigen

Botulinum group expressed a significant decrease in serum PSA level in relation with the induction group (p value ≤ 0.05). Botulinum group had no significant increase in serum PSA level when compared with control group (P value = 0.671). The serum PSA level of each rat in all groups with Mean serum PSA level of each group explained in table (3.6).

Table (3.6): The serum level of prostate specific antigen (PSA) of each rat in all groups with Mean serum PSA level of each group

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	0.629 \pm 0.126
Induction group	1.023 \pm 0.423
Standard treatment group	0.886 \pm 0.188 # ##
Botulinum group	0.685 \pm 0.264 * #
Nicotine group	1.328 \pm 0.356 **

Mean serum level PSA ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. Where * represents significant decrease in serum PSA in comparison with induction group (p value \leq 0.05), # represent no significant increase in comparison with control group (P value $>$ 0.05), ## no significant decrease in serum PSA in comparison with induction group (P value $>$ 0.05) and ** represent significant increase in serum PSA level in comparison with all other groups (p value \leq 0.05).

Control group showed a mean serum PSA level equal to 0.629 ng/ml. Control group expressed no significant decrease in the serum level of PSA in comparison with standard treatment and botulinum groups (p value = 0.054 and 0.671 respectively). Control group possessed a significant decrease in the serum level of PSA with induction group and nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05).

Induction group had a mean serum PSA level equal to 1.023 ng/ml. Induction group showed a significant increase in the serum level of PSA in comparison with control and botulinum groups, in addition had significant decrease in comparison with nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05). Induction group possessed a no significant difference when compared with standard treatment group (P value = 0.299).

Standard treatment group possessed a mean serum PSA level equal to 0.886 ng/ml. Standard treatment group showed a significant decrease in the serum PSA level in comparison with nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05). Standard treatment group expressed no significant difference in serum PSA level with control group,

induction group and botulinum group (P value = 0.054, 0.299 and 0.128 respectively).

Botulinum group had a mean serum PSA level equal to 0.685 ng/ml. Botulinum group possessed a significant decrease in comparison with induction group and nicotine group in Serum PSA level (p value ≤ 0.05). Botulinum group had a no significant difference in comparison with control group and standard treatment group in the level of serum PSA (P value = 0.671 and 0.128 respectively).

Nicotine group had a mean serum level of PSA equal to 1.328 ng/ml . Nicotine group possessed a significant increase in serum level of PSA when compared with control group, induction group, standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value ≤ 0.05). The mean serum PSA level of each group represented in figure (3.12).

Figure (3.12): Mean serum PSA level of each group.

There is no significant increase in serum PSA between control, standard treatment, and botulinum group (p value > 0.05). Induction group showed significant increase in serum PSA in relation to control and botulinum groups (p

value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group showed significant increase in serum PSA with all other groups (p value ≤ 0.05).

3.8 Serum Caspase 3 Level

There were no significant differences in the level of serum caspase 3 (casp3) between all with other groups in post hoc one way ANOVA test. The results of the caspase 3 serum level of all rats in all groups with mean level of each group shown in table (3.7).

Table (3.7): Mean caspase 3 serum levels of all groups

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	3.004 \pm 3.172 *
Induction group	2.024 \pm 0.505 *
Standard treatment group	3.639 \pm 3.176 *
Botulinum group	3.702 \pm 2.547 *
Nicotine group	1.882 \pm 0.338 *

Mean serum Casp3 level ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. * represent no significant difference with all other groups (p value > 0.05).

The mean serum casp3 levels of each group represented in figure (3.13).

Figure (3.13): Mean serum caspase3 of each group showed no significant difference between all groups (P value > 0.05)

3.9 Prostate Tissue Homogenate Tumor Necrosis Factor α Concentration

Botulinum group showed a significant decrease in prostate tissue homogenate tumor necrosis factor α (prostate TNF α) concentration in comparison with induction group (p value ≤ 0.05). On the other hand there were no significant difference between botulinum group and control group (P value = 0.782). The prostate TNF α concentration of all groups table (3.8).

Table (3.8): Prostates TNF α concentration of all groups

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	37.218 \pm 6.415
Induction group	84.054 \pm 67.871
Standard treatment group	48.763 \pm 27.662 *
Botulinum group	41.272 \pm 6.78 *
Nicotine group	95.712 \pm 47.056 **

Mean prostate TNF α concentration ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. * Represent significant decrease in prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (p value ≤ 0.05), # no significant increase in prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with control group (p value > 0.05). **significant increase in

prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with standard treatment and botulinum group (p value ≤ 0.05).

Control group showed a mean prostate TNF α concentration equal 37.218 ng/ml. Control group expressed significant decrease in the prostate TNF α concentration when compared with induction group and nicotine group (p value ≤ 0.05). Control group showed no significant decrease in prostate TNF α concentration when compared with standard treatment group and botulinum group (P value = 0.513 and 0.818).

Induction group had a mean prostate TNF α equal to 84.054 ng/ml. Induction group showed significant increase in the prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with control group, standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value ≤ 0.05). Induction group had no significant decrease in prostate TNF α concentration when compared with nicotine group (P value = 0.509).

Standard treatment group possessed a mean prostate TNF α concentration equal to 48.763 ng/ml. Standard treatment group showed a no significant increase in the prostate TNF α concentration when compared with control group and botulinum group (P value = 0.532 and 0.671 respectively). Standard treatment group had a significant decrease in the prostate TNF α concentration when compared with induction group and nicotine group (p value ≤ 0.05).

Botulinum group had a Mean prostate TNF α equal to 95.712 ng/ml. Botulinum group possessed no significant increase in prostate TNF α concentration when compared with control group and standard treatment group (P value = 0.818 and 0.671 respectively). Botulinum group showed a significant decrease in the prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (p value ≤ 0.05).

Nicotine group had a mean prostate TNF α concentration equal to 1.882 ng/ml . Nicotine group possessed no significant increase in prostate TNF α concentration when compared with induction group (P value = 0.509). Nicotine group had a significant increase in the prostate TNF α concentration in comparison with control group, standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05). The means prostate TNF α concentration of each group represented in figure (3.14).

Figure (3.14): The mean concentration of prostate TNF α of each group. Control, standard treatment and botulinum groups showed a significant difference in comparison with induction and nicotine groups (p value \leq 0.05).

3.10 Prostate Tissue Homogenate PSA Concentration

Botulinum group showed significant reduction in prostate tissue homogenate PSA (prostate PSA) concentration when compared with induction group (p value \leq 0.05). Botulinum group expressed no significant increase in the prostate PSA concentration in comparison with control group (P value =0 0.834). The prostate PSA concentration of all rats on each group and the mean concentration of each group expressed in table (3.9).

Table (3.9): Prostates PSA concentration of all groups

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	0.315 \pm 0.164
Induction group	0.606 \pm 0.394
Standard treatment group	0.411 \pm 0.197 ** #
Botulinum group	0.339 \pm 0.213 * **#
Nicotine group	0.65 \pm 0.24 ##

Mean serum level PSA ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. *Represents significant reduction in prostate PSA concentration in comparison with induction group (p value \leq 0.05), ** significant reduction in prostate PSA concentration in comparison with nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05), #no significant increase in prostate PSA in comparison with control group (p value $>$ 0.05) and ## significant increase in prostate PSA in comparison with control group (p value $>$ 0.05).

Control group showed an Mean prostate PSA concentration equal to 0.315 ng/ml. Control group expressed no significant reduction in the prostate PSA concentration with standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value = 0.404 and 0.834 respectively). Control group possessed a significant reduction in the prostate PSA concentration in comparison with induction group and nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05).

Induction group had a mean prostate PSA concentration equal to 0.606 ng/ml. Induction group showed a significant increase in prostate PSA concentration in comparison with control group and botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05). Induction group possessed a no significant increase in prostate PSA concentration when compared with standard treatment group and nicotine group (P value = 0.095 and 0.702 in that order).

Standard treatment group possessed a Mean prostate PSA concentration equal to 0.411 ng/ml. Standard treatment group showed a significant decrease in the prostate PSA concentration in comparison with nicotine group (p value \leq 0.05).

Standard treatment group expressed no significant increase in the prostate PSA concentration in comparison with control group, botulinum group and no significant reduction with induction group (P value = 0.404, 0.095 and 0.531 respectively).

Botulinum group had a Mean prostate PSA concentration equal to 0.339 ng/ml. Botulinum group possessed a significant reduction in prostate PSA concentration with induction group and nicotine groups (p value ≤ 0.05). Botulinum group had a no significant increase in prostate PSA concentration in comparison with control group and standard treatment group (P value = 0.834 and 0.531 respectively).

Nicotine group had a Mean prostate PSA concentration equal to 0.65 ng/ml . Nicotine group possessed a significant increase in the prostate PSA concentration when compared with control group, standard treatment group and botulinum group (p value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group showed a no significant increase in the prostate PSA concentration when compared with induction group (p value = 0.702). The means prostate PSA concentration of each group represented in figure (3.15).

Figure (3.15): Mean prostate PSA concentration of each group.

There are no significant difference between control, standard treatment, and botulinum group (p value > 0.05). Induction group showed significant difference in relation to control, botulinum and nicotine group (p value ≤ 0.05). Nicotine group showed significant difference with all groups (p value ≤ 0.05).

3.11 Prostate Tissue Caspase 3 Concentration

Botulinum group expressed a significant increase in the prostate casp3 concentration when compared with induction group (p value ≤ 0.05). It is also showed significant difference in comparison with control group (p value ≤ 0.05). The means prostates casp3 concentration of all groups expressed in the table (3.10).

Table (3.10): Prostate casp3 concentration of all groups

Rats group	Mean ng/ml \pm S.D
Control group	2.38 \pm 1.627 **
Induction group	2.151 \pm 1.582 **
Standard treatment group	3.319 \pm 3.504 **
Botulinum group	10.843 \pm 7.731 *
Nicotine group	2.15 \pm 1.444 **

Mean serum level casp3 ng/ml expressed as mean \pm S.D. The S.D represents the standard deviation. * represents significant increase in prostate caspase 3 concentration in comparison with all other groups (p value \leq 0.05) and ** significant reduction in prostate caspase 3 concentration in comparison botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05).

Control group showed a Mean prostate casp3 concentration equal to 2.38ng/ml. Control group expressed no significant increase in the prostate casp3 concentration with induction group, standard treatment group and nicotine group (p value = 0.899, 0.601 and 0.898 respectively).Control group possessed a significant reduction in the prostate casp3 concentration with botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05).

Induction group had a mean prostate casp3 concentration equal to 2.151 ng/ml. Induction group showed no significant increase in the prostate casp3 concentration in comparison with control group, standard treatment group and nicotine group (P value = 0.899, 0.516 and 0.999 respectively). Induction group possessed a significant reduction in prostate casp3 concentration when compared with botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05).

Standard treatment group possessed a Mean prostate casp3 concentration equal to 3.319 ng/ml. Standard treatment group showed a significant reduction in the prostate casp3 concentration in comparison with botulinum group (p value \leq 0.05).Standard treatment group expressed no significant increase in the prostate

casp3 concentration in comparison with control group, induction group and nicotine group (P value = 0.601 0.516 and 0.515 respectively).

Botulinum group had a Mean prostate casp3 concentration equal to 10.843 ng/ml. Botulinum group possessed a significant increase in prostate casp3 concentration with control group, induction group, standard treatment group, botulinum group and nicotine group (p value ≤ 0.05).

Nicotine group had a Mean prostate casp3 concentration equal to 2.15 ng/ml . Nicotine group possessed a no significant increase in the prostate casp3 concentration when compared with control group, induction group and standard treatment group (P value = 0.898, 0.999 and 0.515 in that order). Nicotine group showed a significant reduction in the prostate casp3 concentration when compared with botulinum group (p value ≤ 0.05).

The mean casp3 concentration for all groups showed in figure (3.16).

Figure (3.16): Prostate casp3 concentration

The botulinum group showed a significant increase in prostate caspase 3 concentration when compared with all other groups (p value ≤ 0.05).

3.12 Histopathological Examination:

The section of the prostate tissue of the control group has been expressed in figure (3.17-1). There are unremarkable histopathological changes without sign of inflammation or hyperplasia (Normal prostate tissue).

The section of the prostate gland of the induction group had been shown in figure (3.17-2). There is increase in proliferation of the glandular and stromal tissue with hyperplastic changes and increased number of the glands and cells. There are strong inflammatory reaction with numerous vascular dilation and congestion.

The section of the prostate tissue of standard treatment group showed in figure (3.17-3). There are mild hyperplastic changes with mild inflammatory reaction of the stroma.

Section of the prostate tissue of the botulinum group showed in figure (3.17-4). There are mild inflammatory reactions with mild hyperplasia. and decrease prostate glands secretion. There has scattered apoptotic body shown in at 40X figure (3.17-6).

Section of the prostate gland of the nicotine group showed in figure (3.17-5). There are prostate hyperplasia with strong stromal inflammatory reaction and focal hemorrhage with vascular congestion.

Figure (3.17): Hematoxylin-eosin (H&E) stain of rat prostate gland.

Note: (1) Section of the prostate gland at 10X of the control group injected with normal saline for 43 days. (2) Section of the prostate gland at 10X of the induction group induced with BPH by testosterone injection for 14 days then injected with normal saline for 28 days. (3) Section of the prostate gland at 10X of the standard treatment group induced with BPH by testosterone injection for 14 days then administered standard treatment for 28 days. (4) Section of the prostate gland at 10X of the botulinum group induced with BPH by testosterone injection for 14 days the n injected with botulinum neurotoxin type A at the day 15 and after that administered water by oral gavage from day 16 to 43 of the experiment. (5) Section of the prostate gland at 10X of the nicotine group induced with BPH by testosterone injection for 14 days then injected with botulinum neurotoxin type A at day 15 and after that administered nicotine orally for 28 days. (6) Section of the

prostate gland of the botulinum group showed apoptotic body marked by black arrow.

CHAPTER 4

4 DISCUSSION

The results of this research suggest that the use of botulinum neurotoxin type A for the treatment of BPH in rats show a significant effect to treat BPH disease. It also clarify that there is a central role for nicotine in BPH progression and the majority of botulinum neurotoxin effect may be in due to inhibition of acetylcholine from stimulating prostate nicotinic receptor. The study also clarify that the action of botulinum neurotoxin in reduce prostate weight and volume may be due to its ability to induce apoptosis. Botulinum neurotoxin type A decrease the major inflammatory cytokine TNF α suggest that the Botulinum neurotoxin A reduce inflammation and not cause local inflammation at site of injection. The study showed that continuous daily administration of standard treatment with alfuzosin and dutasteride showed similar effect to single botulinum neurotoxin injection except that botulinum neurotoxin more effective in reducing PSA level and induction of apoptosis.

The nicotine group results showed increase in the size of the prostate gland as it significantly increased the PI, CPV, APV and VPA when compared with botulinum group. This group is created to determine the mechanism of action of botulinum neurotoxin in the treatment of BPH. Researchers suggested that hyperplasia reducing effect of botulinum neurotoxin A is related to its activity on the adrenergic not cholinergic system. The limitation of this conclusion that they studied cholinergic action just by focusing on study of muscarinic receptor implication through bethanicol which is a direct muscarinic receptor agonist but the study not concentrate in the action of prostate nicotinic receptor (75). It was

thought that nicotine proliferative effect on prostate gland attributed to stimulation of nicotinic receptor located on the ganglia of neurons terminate on the prostate portion that lead to secretion of norepinephrine from nerve terminal (76). For the above reasons botulinum neurotoxin A used in the nicotine group to block the release of norepinephrine from nerve terminal. Then, the anticipated effect of nicotine due to its action on the prostate nicotinic receptor as botulinum toxin block acetylcholine, nor-epinephrine and ATP release from nerve terminal (32) . Recent studies directed to understand the role of nicotinic receptor located on the prostate tissue and it is relation to increase cell growth and proliferation. Nicotinic receptor knockdown in PC3 and DU145 cell line lead to increased apoptosis, decreased cell proliferation and decreased phosphorylation of level of AKT and ERK1/2 (77). There is evidence in both in vivo and in vitro animal model studies suggest that treatment with nicotinic acetylcholine receptor blocker such as α -Bungarotoxin could reverse proliferation induced by nicotine (78). Nicotine smoking is also know to inhibit aromatase enzyme responsible for conversion of androgen to estrogen so that is explain the reduction of estradiol 17 β on female rats after chronic exposure to nicotine (79). This mean that nicotine increase testosterone level as wister rats that given aromatase inhibitor showed high testosterone level (80).

Nicotine group showed a significant increase in TNF α level when compared with botulinum group. Its well-known that TNF α cause proliferation in the prostate gland (81).

It obvious from the results that nicotine group showed a significant decrease in prostate casp3 concentration when compared with botulinum group. This may lead to prostate proliferation due to apoptosis inhibiting properties (74).

Botulinum group reduce the weight and the volume as it decrease PI, CPV, APV and VPA of the prostate gland significantly when compared with nicotine group and induction group. The effect of botulinum neurotoxin type A in reducing prostate volume and weight may be due to its inhibitory effect in prostate cell growth due to interruption of nicotinic-acetylcholine receptor (nAChR) signals through inhibition of acetylcholine release from the parasympathetic nerve ending in the prostate gland as shown in figure (1.3). Inhibition of nAChR in the prostate gland may cause decrease in AKT and ERK1/2 expression resulting in decrease prostate cells proliferation. It is also obvious that AKT inhibition cause increase the process of apoptosis by inhibition of caspase 9 activation and at the pre-mitochondrial level before release of cytochrome c as shown in figure (1.4). The ability of botulinum neurotoxin A to significantly decrease TNF α level may lead to prostate proliferation inhibition since TNF α antagonism reduces benign prostatic hyperplasia (82). Botulinum group decrease TNF α concentration in the prostate gland suggest that botulinum toxin not cause inflammatory reaction at site of injection which is the major adverse effect of botulinum neurotoxin A (83).

The botulinum group showed to decrease level TNF α significantly both in serum and prostate gland when compared with induction group as shown in table (3.5) and table (3.8). TNF α have a central role in inflammation (84). Botulinum neurotoxin have anti-inflammatory effect in reducing mast cell degranulation in induced arthritis in rats (85). Botulinum neurotoxin antagonizes the action of acetylcholine in both muscarinic and nicotinic receptors by inhibiting acetylcholine release from nerve ending (86). Antagonizing the muscarinic receptor in rat's leukocyte decreases the T-cell and antibody proliferative responses. Muscarinic receptor antagonist also blocks the turpentine-induced white blood cells infiltration, inhibited chemotaxis of white blood cells toward

other neutrophil, monocyte and lymphocyte chemoattractants. For this reason block of nicotinic and muscarinic receptors has shown to reduce inflammatory responses (87).

Botulinum group showed to decrease PSA level significantly both in serum and in the prostate tissue when compared with nicotine and induction groups as shown in table (3.6) and table (3.9). Botulinum neurotoxin showed to decrease PSA in humans (88). As we mentioned earlier PSA is secreted from prostate gland (89). This result is supported by evidence of decreased secretion in the glandular part of the prostate tissue histopathological examination of section of the prostate gland as shown in figure (3.17-4). The ultrasonography of the ventral lobe of the prostate gland showed hyperechogenic ventral lobe that may be due to decrease prostate secretion as showed in figure (3.9).

The anti-hyperplasia effect of botulinum neurotoxin type A may be due in part to action of botulinum neurotoxin to induce apoptosis in prostate cells (90). This also explained by our results that include increased prostate casp3 concentration showed in table (3.10) and the appearance of apoptotic body in the histopathological examination showed in figure (3.17-6).

Botulinum group showed increase in the expression of caspase 3 in the prostate tissue when compared with induction group. Botulinum neurotoxin type A induce apoptosis in rat prostate (91),(92). This effect may be due to the implication of the botulinum neurotoxin type A in the blocking of nicotinic acetylcholine receptor $\alpha 5$ (nAChR $\alpha 5$) that may result in decrease AKT that lead to increase apoptosis both at pre-mitochondrial and post-mitochondrial level as shown in figure (1.4). The evidence of apoptosis supported by this research

results, histopathological examination showed expression of apoptotic body in the section of the prostate gland at 40X as shown in figure (3.17-6).

Standard treatment group decrease PI, CPV, APV and VPA significantly when compared with induction group. Standard treatment group showed no significant increase in PI, CPV, APV and VPA in comparison with botulinum group as shown in table (3.1), table (3.2) and table (3.3). Results also showed that despite this effect standard treatment group has not shown a significant increase in caspase 3 level in tissue or blood as shown in table (3.7) and table (3.10). these finding suggest that standard treatment group reduce size and weight of the prostate gland by a process other than apoptosis. $\alpha 1$ adrenergic antagonists shown to decrease proliferation by activity that include its action on blocking $\alpha 1A$ receptors and by other mechanism that is not related to $\alpha 1$ A receptor like DNA damage as shown in figure (1.5). Researches showed that dutasteride cause autophagy through down regulation of insulin like growth factor 1 (IGF-1) in the stromal cells of the prostate glands (93).

Standard treatment group showed a significant reduction in serum TNF α and prostate TNF α when compared with induction group. Standard treatment group showed no significant increase in TNF α level when compared with botulinm group as shown table (3.5) and table (3.8). Dutasteride treatment restored the expression of estrogen receptor β (ER β) that was downregulated in the inflamed prostate. ER β showed anti-inflammatory effect in human prostate (94). Alfuzosin showed to reduce chronic prostatitis (95).

Standard treatment group showed no significant reduction in serum level and prostate concentration of PSA when compared with induction group. On the other botulinum group showed significant decrease in PSA level with induction group.

These results suggest this treatment reduce PSA to level that is enough to show a no significant increase when compare with control group but not enough to develop a significant decrease in PSA level when compared with induction group. The explanation of this results may be due to the treatment time is not sufficient to show the full activity of this standard treatment. As we mention earlier standard treatment composed of 5 α reductase inhibitors (Dutasteride) and α 1 adrenergic receptor blocker (Alfuzosin hydrochloride). Its well know that dutasteride reduce PSA level significantly after six month of treatment as FDA announced that the reduction in PSA with 5 α reductase occur after 6 months by 50% (96). Alfuzosin hydrochloride show no significant decrease in PSA level between untreated patient group and patient group administered alfuzosin for at least one month (97). Prostate specific antigen (PSA) produced in prostate tissue and secreted into the lumen (52). The ultrasonography of rats in standard treatment group showed hypoechogenic ventral prostate that suggests that standard treatment may not interfere with prostate secretion and that may explain why there was no significant reduction on PSA level. Results suggest that standard treatment not induce apoptosis as shown in table (3.10). There is no significant increase in prostate caspase 3 concentrations in comparison with control, induction and nicotine groups. Botulinum group significantly increase caspase 3 concentration in the prostate tissue when compared with standard treatment group. This result may be due in part to the effect of dutasteride in causing autophagy and thus inhibiting apoptosis (98). Alfuzosin not considered as a strong initiator of apoptosis process (99).

There is no significant difference in the plasma level of caspase 3 between all groups but there is significant difference between some groups in prostate caspase 3 concentration in prostate tissue. This finding suggest that plasma level of

caspase 3 is not reliable biomarker and its not useful to examine the actual apoptotic activity that happen in prostate gland on rats induced BPH. The possible explanation for this result is that in apoptosis the apoptotic body formed which consist of intact plasma membrane surround the cytoplasm and organelles with or without fragment of the nucleus, then this apoptotic body mainly removed through phagocyte engulfment. This mean that the cell component not released into interstitial area surrounding the cell so, that's explain why inflammation not occur in apoptosis (100). This lead us to clear a concept that if content such as caspase 3 not released from apoptotic body, it may mean it not reach blood in significant amount so, we cannot consider caspase 3 level in the plasma as an accurate biomarker.

5 Conclusion:

- 1- Botulinum group showed to reduce weight and size of the prostate gland. botulinum neurotoxin A showed to reduce inflammation and prostate specific antigen. botulinum neurotoxin A showed a strong ability to induce apoptosis in the prostate gland.
- 2- Nicotine group showed that nicotine treatment after botulinum neurotoxin type A injection tends to eliminate the activity of botulinum neurotoxin. This can be considering a strong indicator that botulinum neurotoxin type A exerts its effect by inhibiting acetylcholine from stimulating nicotinic receptor.
- 3- The effect of botulinum neurotoxin A seems to be mainly related to the effect on the interruption of acetylcholine – nicotinic receptor axis.
- 4- The study showed strong evidence that both botulinum neurotoxin A and standard treatment showed similar efficacy in reducing prostate weight, size, and inflammation in induced BPH in male rats. The botulinum neurotoxin A decrease PSA level more than standard treatment. Botulinum group induce apoptosis while standard treatment cannot induce apoptosis.

6 Recommendation:

The study suggests that further researches needed to compare the effect of repetitive dose of botulinum neurotoxin type A with standard treatment in long term treatment.

The study encourage other researcher to focus on prostate nicotinic receptor as drug target to develop new drugs act by antagonizing prostate nicotinic receptor effects.

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الخلاصة

الهدف: لتفسير ميكانيكية عمل ومقارنة تأثير السم العصبي البوتليني نوع A مع العلاج الأساسي (الفازوسين و دوتاستيراييد) في علاج تضخم البروستات الحميد المحفز في ذكور الجرذان.

النظرية: خمس مجموعات كل واحدة تتكون من ١٠ جرذان. مجموعة السيطرة حقنت سائل ملحي داخل الصفاق لمدة ٤٢ يوم. مجموعة التحفيز ومجموعة العلاج الأساسي ومجموعة البوتلينيوم ومجموعة النيكوتين حقنت على تطوير تضخم البروستات الحميد عن طريق حقن التيستوستيرون. بعد ذلك مجموعة التحفيز حقنت سائل ملحي لمدة ٢٨ يوم. مجموعة العلاج التقليدي اعطيت العلاج المتكون من الفازوسين ودوتاستيراييد لمدة ٢٨ يوم. مجموعة البوتلينيوم حقنت بالبوتلينيوم نيوروتوكسين A داخل البروستات في اليوم ١٥. مجموعة النيكوتين حقنت بالبوتلينيوم نيوروتوكسين A داخل البروستات في اليوم ١٥ وبعدها اعطيت نيكوتين لمدة ٢٧ يوم.

بعدها اجري سونار لفص البروستات تحت الصفاق. بعد ذلك تم قياس وزن الجرذان والتضحية بها.بعدها استخرجت البروستات وقيس حجمها ووزنها. تم عمل اختبار الأليزا والهستوباثولوجي.

النتائج: مجموعة البوتلينيوم والسيطرة والعلاج التقليدي اظهرت تقليل بارز في مساحة البروستات الصفحي عند المقارنة مع مجموعة التحفيز والنيكوتين. مجموعات البوتلينيوم والعلاج التقليدي والسيطرة اظهرت تقليل بارز في مستوى عامل نخر الورم الفا في المصل عند المقارنة مع مجموعتي التحفيز والنيكوتين. مجموعتي البوتلينيوم والسيطرة اظهرتا تقليل بارز في مستوى مستضد بروتينات نوعي في المصل عند المقارنة مع مجموعتي التحفيز. مجموعة البوتلينيوم اظهرت زيادة بارزة في مستوى كاسبيز ٣ في البروستات عند المقارنة مع مجموعات السيطرة والتحفيز والعلاج التقليدي والنيكوتين.

الاستنتاج:

حقن السم العصبي البوتليني A في البروستات يقلل تضخم البروستات بشكل جزئي عن طريق منع تحفيز مستقبل النيكوتين. البوتلينيوم يمتلك فعالية مثل العلاج التقليدي ويمتلك افضلية اقتصادية كونه حقنة واحدة. مستقبل النيكوتين قد يكون له دور رئيسي في تضخم البروستات الحميد. مستقبل النيكوتين في البروستات من الممكن ان يكون هدف جديد للدراسات المستقبلية لتطوير ادوية جديدة فعالة لمعالجة تضخم البروستات الحميد. نحتاج مزيد من الدراسات لمقارنة مفعول الجرعة المتكررة من حقن السم العصبي البوتليني A مع العلاج الاساسي.

جمهورية العراق
وزارة التعليم العالي والبحث العلمي
الجامعة المستنصرية
كلية الصيدلة

تأثير السم العصبي البوتليني نوع A في علاج تضخم البروستات الحميد المحفز في
ذكور الجرذان

من قبل
غازي فيصل ماجد
(بكالوريوس صيدلة ٢٠١٥)

رسالة مقدمة إلى
فرع الأدوية والسموم والى لجنة الدراسات العليا في كلية الصيدلة/الجامعة المستنصرية كجزء من متطلبات
الحصول على شهادة الماجستير علم الأدوية والسموم

بإشراف

الاستاذ المساعد الدكتور
اسراء برهان رؤوف

الاستاذ الدكتور
مصطفى غازي العباسي

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